

PRINCIPLES OF USING THE DUAL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE TRAINING OF EXPERT PERSONNEL IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: Today, the training of specialists in our country is becoming a major problem. Measures aimed at preventing this actual problem are increasing day by day. In this article, discussions and proposals aimed at solving the problem of developing the education system using the dual education system are presented.

Keywords: Professional staff, dual education, Practical training, Work-related training, Coordinated training programs, Mentoring and planning, Industry cooperation

Main part: A specialist is a concept that represents a person or group of people who possess the morale, knowledge and skills and specialize in a field or fields. Specialist personnel are persons who are prepared to perform tasks in the specified field with their specific knowledge and skills and who strive to develop skills.

Specialist personnel are individuals who are highly qualified in their field, easily adapt to new developments, and have a high level of experience and knowledge to solve problems. Constant learning and interaction is important to improve their skills and knowledge of their fields.

Professional staff, up-to-date in their field, adept at finding solutions that fit the industry's requirements, and strengthen their commitment to industry development. Their interest and talent for self-development and learning new knowledge will help them solve problems and tasks in the field.

In addition, professional personnel constantly collaborate with teachers, mentors or other professional contacts to learn and develop innovations in their field. It is important that they participate in a continuous learning process to develop knowledge and skills that are relevant to the innovations in the field.

The existence and development of specialist personnel in every sphere of society are the most important conditions for the adoption of innovations and their successful implementation in practice.

The main principles of using the dual education system in the training of specialist personnel are as follows:

- ✚ Practical training: The dual education system plays an important role in the training of specialist personnel through practical training. Students will have the opportunity to put theoretical knowledge into practice and will be able to get acquainted with, strengthen and develop practical work for their mastery.
- ✚ Work-related training: The dual education system gives students the opportunity to gain practical experience through work-related training. These experiences help students get to know the industry, improve their skills in practice, and carry industry-related knowledge.
- ✚ Coordinated educational programs: Dual education system provides coordinated educational programs for the training of specialist personnel. These programs combine theoretical and practical knowledge to help equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to meet the demands of the industry.
- ✚ Mentoring and Planning: Dual education system provides students with mentoring and planning opportunities. This provides additional support for educational pathways designed in conjunction with personal development for students.
- ✚ Collaboration with the industry: The dual education system enhances collaboration with the industry and gives students the opportunity to collaborate with companies, institutes or other organizations in the industry. This will help students stay up-to-date with industry news, gain hands-on experience, and develop professional connections.

The regulation on the procedure for establishing a dual system of training in professional education of the Republic of Uzbekistan is approved. According to the

regulations, in the implementation of dual education, the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, other legal documents, does.

Professional educational institutions where dual education is organized are determined by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The possibilities of educational institutions, where dual education is planned, can be studied with the participation of experts appointed by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education.

Conclusion: The use of the dual education system is important for familiarizing specialists with practical work, introducing them to innovations in the field, and developing their skills through coordinated training programs.

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